

"ILLUMINATING THE GENETIC LANDSCAPE: INVESTIGATING BRINJAL DIVERSITY VIA QUANTITATIVE TRAIT ANALYSIS"Gal Chetan¹, M. M. Pandya^{2*}, N. A. Patel², Rutvik J. Joshi¹ and Bhavya Desai¹¹Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, B. A. College of Agriculture, Anand Agricultural University, Anand-388110, India.²Main Vegetable Research Station, Anand Agricultural University, Anand-388110, India.

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Abstract

This study aimed to explore the genetic diversity of brinjal (*Solanum melongena* L.) genotypes and its implications for breeding programs. A comprehensive investigation was conducted on sixty brinjal accessions, utilizing morphological characterization and Mahalanobis's D^2 statistics to assess the genotypic variations. The genotypes were classified into distinct clusters based on their cluster means and inter-cluster distances, providing insights into the extent of genetic dissimilarities. The identification of superior genotypes with desirable traits holds promising prospects for breeding programs, particularly for enhancing fruit yield and addressing deficiencies in branch density and fruit volume. Additionally, genotypes from a cluster exhibiting early flowering characteristics were highlighted, offering potential opportunities for the development of early flowering cultivars. The study further examined the contributions of different traits to genetic divergence, with total soluble sugars and fruits per plant emerging as significant influencers. These findings provide valuable insights and guidance for breeders, empowering them to make informed decisions in selecting parental combinations and harnessing the genetic diversity of brinjal germplasm. By leveraging this diversity, breeders can expedite the development of brinjal cultivars with enhanced traits and increased productivity. Overall, this study contributes to the body of knowledge on brinjal genetics and serves as a valuable resource for the advancement of breeding programs in this important vegetable crop. By incorporating genotypes from different clusters, breeders can maximize the potential for developing brinjal varieties that are well-adapted to various agro-climatic conditions and exhibit improved nutritional qualities and resistance to pests and diseases.

Key words - *Solanum melongena* L., genetic diversity, pests and diseases.

Introduction

Brinjal, a vegetable crop of significant importance in India, is scientifically known as *Solanum melongena* L. Within brinjal, different varieties can be distinguished based on the shape and size of their fruits (Saini & Sharma, 2015). The large, round or egg-shaped fruits belong to var. *esculentum*, while the cylindrical and elongated types are classified as var. *sorparentium*. The dwarf brinjal plants fall under var. *depressum*. Brinjal, belonging to the Solanaceae family, is a cross-pollinated crop with a chromosome number of $2n=24$. The *Solanum* genus comprises approximately 200 species that bear tubers and 1800 species that do not.

The diversity within brinjal is manifested through variations in its morphological characteristics, genetic composition, and agronomic traits. This diversity holds immense value for the development of improved cultivars with desirable traits, including disease resistance, fruit quality, and high yield potential. Therefore, understanding the diversity present in brinjal germplasm is crucial for effective breeding programs and conservation endeavors.

To explore the diversity within brinjal, researchers have employed various approaches, including morphological characterization, molecular markers, and biochemical analyses. These methods have contributed to our understanding of the extent of diversity within the crop. Such investigations have revealed substantial variation within brinjal germplasm, which serves as a valuable resource for crop improvement.

Morphological characterization involves the evaluation of observable traits such as plant height, leaf morphology, flower characteristics, and fruit shape, color, and size. Studies utilizing this approach have unveiled diverse variations in these traits among different brinjal genotypes. Fruit shape, for example, can range from round to oval, elongated, or even cylindrical.

Biochemical analyses have also contributed to the exploration of diversity in brinjal. These analyses focus on biochemical markers, including enzymes and proteins, to reveal variations in metabolic pathways and biochemical composition (Khokhar *et al.*, 2017). By utilizing biochemical markers, researchers can identify genotypes with specific desirable traits, such as enhanced nutritional value or resistance to pests and diseases. The diverse germplasm of brinjal provides a wide range of genetic resources for crop improvement. Utilizing this diversity holds the potential to develop brinjal varieties that are well-adapted to different agro-climatic conditions, possess

improved nutritional qualities, and exhibit resistance to biotic and abiotic stresses. Furthermore, conserving diverse brinjal germplasm is crucial to prevent genetic erosion and ensure the long-term sustainability of this important vegetable crop.

Materials and Methods

The primary objective of this investigation was to gather insights into the genetic variation present in brinjal (*Solanum melongena* L.). The study was conducted during the *kharif-rabi* season of 2020-21 at the Main Vegetable Research Station, Anand. A total of sixty diverse brinjal accessions were included in the experiment, arranged in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Plants were transplanted at a spacing of 90 cm x 60 cm between and within rows. Random allocation of genotypes to the plots was performed within each replication. To assess morphological diversity, fourteen different characteristics were examined, and their mean values were used for analysis. The recorded data for these traits underwent analysis of variance and Mahalanobis D^2 statistics using the Spar 1 software to estimate the level of morphological diversity. For grouping the genotypes into distinct clusters, a multivariate analysis of genetic divergence based on Mahalanobis D^2 statistics, originally described by Rao (1952), was employed. To accomplish this clustering, Tocher's method (Rao, 1952) was applied.

Results and Discussion

Genetic diversity assessment was conducted on a set of sixty brinjal genotypes by utilizing Mahalanobis's D^2 statistics. This analysis allowed for the identification of superior genotypes that could potentially be utilized in breeding programs. Additionally, cluster mean and inter-cluster distance were considered as criteria for selecting the most promising genotypes. The composition of the clusters is detailed in Table 2, with cluster I being the largest and comprising 52 genotypes. Cluster II contained only three genotypes, while clusters III, IV, V, VI, and VII were found to be monogenotypic.

Intra and inter cluster distance

To further evaluate the genetic diversity, inter-cluster and intra-cluster distances were examined. Notably, the largest inter-cluster distance was observed between cluster IV and V, followed by the distance between cluster V and VI. On the other hand, the smallest inter-cluster distance was found between cluster I and V. These distances serve as indicators of the genetic dissimilarities between clusters.

Cluster Means of Various Characters

Genotypes from cluster V and cluster VI were utilized in hybridization to enhance the number of fruits per plant and fruit yield per plant. This approach was selected because genotypes from both clusters exhibited significant diversity for these particular traits. By crossing these genetically distinct parents, breeders aimed to combine and amplify the desired traits, ultimately leading to improved fruit production. In another breeding strategy, genotypes from cluster VI and cluster VII were employed in pedigree breeding. This method aimed to address the deficiency of low branches per plant and low fruit volume observed in certain genotypes. By carefully selecting and crossing individuals from these clusters, breeders sought to gradually eliminate these undesirable traits while promoting the development of plants with increased branch density and larger fruit size. By consciously selecting and combining individuals with desired traits from these diverse backgrounds, breeders aimed to expedite the improvement process and develop plant varieties with enhanced overall productivity.

To develop early flowering cultivars, breeders selected genotypes from cluster III. These genotypes were chosen due to their unique characteristics and ability to flower earlier than other clusters. They can be used directly as parents in a breeding program or incorporated into a heterosis breeding program. The utilization of genotypes from cluster III brings unique genetic diversity into the breeding program, which can enhance the chances of obtaining early flowering cultivars. Early flowering is a crucial trait as it allows plants to complete their life cycle and produce fruits or seeds earlier, thereby extending the growing season and potentially improving productivity. By incorporating these genotypes, breeders increase the genetic variation available for selection, ultimately leading to the development of cultivars that exhibit early flowering along with other desirable characteristics. *Characters Contribution towards Genetic Divergence*

An analysis of the contributions of different traits to the overall genetic divergence was carried out. Table 2 presents the inter-cluster and intra-cluster variances, as well as the ratio (R^2) of inter-cluster variance to total variance for fourteen different characters. The traits with the highest R^2 values were total soluble sugars and fruits per plant, indicating their significant contributions to genetic diversity. Peduncle length, fruit length, average fruit weight, fruit girth, fruit volume, fruit yield per plant, plant height, and branches per plant also exhibited substantial contributions. These findings align with Devmore *et al.* (2015) and Sadarunnisa *et al.* (2015) that have highlighted the importance of fruit weight and fruit length in genetic divergence.

Additionally, the inter-cluster coefficient of variance was calculated to assess the variation within clusters. Traits such as total soluble sugars, fruits per plant, fruit length, fruit volume, peduncle length, and fruit girth exhibited the highest coefficients of variance. These results provide insights into the extent of diversity present within individual clusters.

The outcomes of this study are consistent with the work conducted by Madhavi *et al.* (2015) and Rekha and Celine (2015), who also investigated genetic divergence in brinjal genotypes and categorized them into clusters. Taking into account the high inter-cluster values, it is recommended to perform hybridization experiments involving genotypes from cluster IV and V to capitalize on maximum hybrid

vigor and obtain desirable segregants. Notably, the mean performance and genetic distance analysis suggest that the hybridization of AB 19-03 from cluster IV with AB 19-08 from cluster V would likely result in the development of valuable genetic stocks. Furthermore, the contribution percentages of different traits to the overall genetic divergence were presented in Table 4. Total soluble sugars emerged as the most influential trait, contributing significantly (32.4%) to the total genetic divergence. Total soluble solids and fruits per plant also made substantial contributions of 16.70% and 12.40%, respectively. Conversely, fruit yield per plant, total phenols, days to 50% flowering, moisture content, fruit girth, average fruit weight, peduncle length, branches per plant, fruit volume, plant height, and fruit length exhibited relatively lower contributions to the overall genetic divergence.

Conclusion

To sum up, this study has yielded important findings regarding the genetic variation in brinjal genotypes. The knowledge gained from identifying superior genotypes, evaluating cluster means, analyzing inter-cluster distances, and understanding trait contributions to genetic divergence holds great importance for breeding programs. These insights serve as a valuable guide for breeders, enabling them to make informed decisions when selecting parent combinations for crossbreeding, pedigree breeding, and the development of early flowering cultivars. By purposefully integrating genotypes from diverse clusters, breeders can expedite the improvement process and cultivate brinjal varieties that exhibit higher productivity and desirable traits.

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Table 1 Distribution of 60 genotypes of brinjal into 7 clusters on the basis of D2-statistics

Cluster	Number of genotypes	Name of the genotypes
I	52	AB 15-06, AB 15-08, AB 15-10, AB 16-02, AB 16-12, AB 17-05, AB 17-06, AB 17-07, AB 17-09, AB 17-16, AB 17-17, AB 17-25, AB 17-27, AB 18-05, AB 18-06, AB 20-21, AB 18-09, AB 18-10, AB 19-01, AB 19-02, AB 19-03, AB 19-05, AB 19-07, AB 19-09, AB 19-10, AB 20-03, AB 20-04, AB 20-05, AB 20-06, AB 20-07, AB 20-08, AB 20-09, AB 20-10, AB 20-12, AB 20-13, AB 20-14, AB 20-15, AB 20-16, AB 20-17, AB 20-20, NBR 14-01, NBR 18-01 JBL 18-02, JBR 18-10, JBR 18-12, JBL 18-15, JBR 18-17, GOB 1, GAOB 2, GRB 5, GAB 6, Swarna Mani Black
II	3	AB 7-02, AB 17-20, AB 20-18
III	1	AB 17-28
IV	1	AB 19-03
V	1	AB 19-08
VI	1	AB 20-19
VII	1	AB 20-22

Table 4 Contribution of various traits towards total genetic divergence

Sr. No.	Characters	Time ranked first	Contribution (%)
1.	Days to 50 per cent flowering	34	1.90
2.	Fruit length (cm)	161	9.10
3.	Fruit girth (cm)	48	2.70
4.	Average fruit weight (g)	42	2.40
5.	Fruits per plant	220	12.40
6.	Peduncle length (cm)	62	3.50
7.	Plant height (cm)	92	5.20
8.	Branches per plant	64	3.60
9.	Fruit yield per plant (kg)	25	1.40
10.	Fruit volume (cc)	83	4.70
11.	Moisture content (%)	36	2.00
12.	Total phenols (mg/100g)	34	1.90
13.	Total soluble sugars (%)	573	32.40
14.	Total soluble solids (°Brix)	296	16.70
Total		1770	99.90

Table 2 Average intra and inter cluster (D²) value for 60 genotypes of brinjal

Clusters	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
I	44.57	11.81	13.98	81.68	35.86	5.73	83.25	3.13	2.71	115.73	77.01	89.21	2.71	6.23
II	43.11	19.78	9.44	63.33	38.15	8.81	93.37	2.61	2.58	86.44	74.80	86.23	4.69	6.38
III	40.00	10.66	21.23	69.66	46.00	4.63	118.33	3.66	3.93	197.00	84.66	118.08	3.41	6.83
IV	46.00	11.66	10.73	73.00	41.40	4.95	71.16	3.83	3.19	145.00	80.33	71.33	7.38	5.72
V	48.00	17.46	15.60	146.33	20.73	7.70	86.33	3.00	1.83	105.33	74.98	54.66	1.98	6.19
VI	40.00	8.00	12.10	83.33	84.70	6.60	81.13	4.33	4.10	69.33	80.00	78.14	5.23	5.99
VII	44.66	8.76	19.50	87.66	26.33	6.33	118.66	1.89	2.64	189.00	82.30	88.00	6.30	6.93

Note: R²: Ratio of the inter cluster variance to the total variance

CV_b % : Inter cluster coefficient of variation

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|---------------------------|-----------------------------|-------------------------------|-----------------------------|---------------------------------|
| 1. Days to 50 % flowering | 4. Average fruit weight (g) | 7. Plant height (cm) | 10. Fruit volume (cc) | 13. Total soluble sugars (%) |
| 2. Fruit length (cm) | 5. Fruits per plant | 8. Branches per plant | 11. Moisture content (%) | 14. Total soluble solid (°Brix) |
| 3. Fruit girth (cm) | 6. Peduncle length (cm) | 9. Fruit yield per plant (kg) | 12. Total phenols (mg/100g) | |

Table 3 Cluster mean for 14 different characters in 60 genotypes of brinjal

Clusters	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII
I	200.00	405.76	372.04	831.94	290.79	686.72	557.49
II		214.86	650.94	546.54	418.79	650.84	431.29
III			0	876.11	720.39	895.51	408.13
IV				0	1134.32	516.98	296.27
V					0	1068.16	809.98
VI						0	704.22
VII							0